

we have observed that if these acids are allowed to remain in sulphuric acid for more than 6 hours, the yields of thiochromanones decrease considerably.

For the syntheses of Mannich bases (II) equimolar quantities of a thiochromanone, paraformaldehyde and a secondary or primary amine hydrochloride were heated under reflux for 6 hours in dry benzene as a solvent. The reaction mixture was acidified with 5-10 drops of A.R. hydrochloric acid, at the start of the reaction. In most of the cases, during the reaction, the Mannich bases separated as crystalline solids and did not need any concentration of the solvent for their isolation. Absolute alcohol and 95% alcohol, when substituted as solvents, lowered the yield of the Mannich bases considerably (less than 5%).

All the Mannich bases (II) (as hydrochlorides) were found to be stable. Their aqueous solutions on standing did not decompose and (II) could be isolated on evaporation. The free bases were sticky and low-melting compounds, which were not crystallisable. However, the bases were characterised through their picrates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thiophenols and β -Thiophenoxypropionic Acids.—The thiophenols, viz., thiophenol, *p*-chloro-, *o*-chloro- and *p*-methyl-thiophenols, required for the work were prepared according to the method of Tarbell and Fukushima (*loc. cit.*). These were converted into the corresponding β -thiophenoxypropionic acids by condensing with β -propiolactone (Gresham, *loc. cit.*).

o-Chlorothiophenol was prepared from *o*-chloroaniline in 62.5% yield, b.p. 80°/1 mm.

β -(*o*-Chlorothiophenoxy)-propionic acid was obtained from *o*-chlorothiophenol in 88% yield, m.p. 89-90°. It was recrystallised from ethanol. (Found: S, 14.67. $C_9H_8O_2ClS$ requires S, 14.78%).

Thiochromanones.—The cyclisation of the above β -thiophenoxypropionic acids to thiochromanones was effected with 98% H_2SO_4 (Krollpfeiffer and Schultze, *loc. cit.*). The preparation of 8-chlorothiochromanone is given below.

8-Chlorothiochromanone.— β -(*o*-Chlorothiophenoxy)-propionic acid (5 g.) was dissolved in 98% H_2SO_4 (50 g., cold) with an immediate development of a red coloration. After standing at room temperature for 6 hours, the reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice (200 g.). The solid (4.2 g.) separating was first washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with cold water. It was dried and then recrystallised from 50% ethanol; yield 92%, m.p. 86-87°. (Found: S, 15.95. C_9H_7OClS requires S, 16.11%). Its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone melted at 267° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.63. $C_{15}H_{11}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 14.80%).

3-Dialkylamino-alkyl-thiochroman-4-one Hydrochlorides: The Mannich Reaction.—A mixture of the thiochromanone (0.01 M) and paraformaldehyde (0.01 M) in dry benzene (25 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 30 minutes. To this was added 0.01 M of a secondary or primary amine hydrochloride (the amines used were dimethylamine, piperidine, morpholine, benzylamine di-*n*-propylamine and piperazine).

POSSIBLE ANTIAMOEBIIC AGENTS

TABLE I
Mannich bases (hydrochloride) (II).

Sl. No.	R' & R''	R ₁ & R ₂	M.P.	Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.		M.P.	Mol. formula.	% Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
1.	H	Piperidyl	176°	67%	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ ONClS	4.54	4.71	10.48	10.75	153°	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₄ S	11.21	11.43
2.	...	Morpholinyl	157°	50	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₃ NClS	4.71	4.67	10.35	10.68	128°	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₄ S	11.13	11.38
3.	...	Benzyl	168°	71	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ONClS	4.31	4.38	10.21	10.01	...	...	...	...
4.	6-Me	Piperidyl	164°	60	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ ONClS	4.32	4.49	...	...	...	...	...	...
5.	...	Morpholinyl	171°	52	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₃ NClS	4.36	4.47	...	...	...	...	...	...
6.	...	Benzyl	188°	80	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ ONClS	4.30	4.20	...	...	...	...	...	...
7.	...	Dimethyl	157°	75	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ ONClS	4.70	4.79	11.67	11.78	...	...	...	...
8.	6-Cl	Piperidyl	194°	74	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ONCl ₂ S	4.30	4.22	9.48	9.64	160°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₄ ClS	10.25	10.68
9.	...	Morpholinyl	166°	72	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₃ NClS ₂	4.01	4.19	9.25	9.58	157°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ ClS	10.32	10.64
10.	...	Benzyl	197°	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ONCl ₂ S	4.00	3.96	9.10	9.04	...	...	...	...
11.	...	Dimethyl	160°	80	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ONCl ₂ S	4.90	4.79	10.84	10.96	...	...	...	...
12.	•8-Cl	Piperidyl	211°	78	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ONCl ₂ S	4.00	4.22	9.54	9.64	164°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₄ ClS	10.32	10.68
13.	...	Morpholinyl	169°	75	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₃ NCl ₂ S	4.20	4.19	9.35	9.58	174°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ ClS	10.15	10.64
14.	...	Benzyl	195°	77	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ONCl ₂ S	3.78	3.96	9.21	9.04	...	...	...	...
15.	...	Dimethyl	178°	76	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ ONCl ₂ S	4.69	4.79	10.83	10.96	159°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₄ ClS	11.13	11.56
16.	...	Di-n-propyl	151°	45	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ ONCl ₂ S	...	...	9.15	9.07	...	...	...	...
17.	...	Piperazine	98°	50	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S ₂	4.73	4.83	11.21	11.03	260°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₁₆ N ₆ Cl ₄ S ₂	11.30	11.60

* Vide structure (VI)

The reaction mixture was acidified with 5-10 drops of A.R. HCl and refluxed for 3-6 hours, during which most of the Mannich bases separated in crystalline forms. After cooling, the reaction mixture was filtered and the product obtained was washed with dry benzene and finally recrystallised from absolute alcohol.

The compounds (as HCl salts) are mostly soluble in hot water (excepting the products from benzylamine) and are very stable. The intense and bright red colour with a drop of H_2SO_4 (conc.) is the most characteristic property of all the Mannich bases reported in the present work. The Mannich bases (II) were characterised by preparing their picrates.

Picrates.—The compound (II: 0.05 g.) was dissolved in hot water (10 c.c.) and mixed under shaking with a saturated aqueous solution of picric acid (10 c.c.). An immediate turbidity appeared and crystalline picrates separated on cooling. These were filtered and purified by recrystallisation from ethanol.

Decomposition of the Products.—The compounds (8,9 and 13 of Table I) was dissolved in water (10 c.c.) separately. After standing at room temperature for 24 hours, 1 g. each of the original products separated, showing no indication of decomposition. The melting points and analyses of the Mannich bases and their picrates are shown in Table I.

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